

Polyesterase activity is widespread in the family IV carboxylesterases from bacteria

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Family IV carboxylesterases show discrete substrate preference and promiscuity.
- Polyesterase activity appears to be widespread in the family IV carboxylesterases.
- Thermostability of polyesterases can be improved using ancestral reconstruction.
- Established PETases also show high hydrolytic activity against other polyesters.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Enzyme-based depolymerization of plastics, including polyesters, has emerged as a promising approach for plastic waste recycling and reducing environmental plastic pollution. Currently, most of the known polyester-degrading enzymes are represented by a few natural and engineered PETases from the carboxylesterase family V. To identify novel groups of polyesterases, we selected 25 proteins from the carboxylesterase family IV, which share 22 % to 80 % sequence identity to the metagenomic thermophilic polyesterase IS12. All purified proteins were found to be active against chromogenic *para*-nitrophenyl esters with a preference for short acyl chains. Screening for polyesterase activity using emulsified polyesters demonstrated the presence of hydrolytic activity against bis(benzoyloxyethyl) terephthalate (3PET), polycaprolactone (PCL), and polylactic acid (PLA) in all tested proteins. Biochemical characterization of four selected polyesterases revealed high thermostability in

Abbreviations: 3-PET, bis(benzoyloxyethyl) terephthalate; BA, benzoic acid; BHET, bis(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalate; EPPS, (N-2-hydroxyethyl)piperazine-N-(3-propane sulfonic acid); HEB, hydroxyethyl benzoate; ISPETase, *Ideonella sakaiensis* PETase; LCC, leaf-branch compost cutinase; MHET, mono(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalate; PBAT, poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate); PBS, poly(butylene succinate); PBT, polybutylene terephthalate; PCL, polycaprolactone; PE, polyethylene; PEA, poly(ethylene adipate); PEN, poly(ethylene naphthalate); PET, polyethylene terephthalate; PGA, polyglycolic acid; PHB, poly(hydroxybutyrate); PLA, polylactic acid; pNP, *para*-nitrophenyl; PP, polypropylene; PS, polystyrene; PTT, poly(trimethylene terephthalate); PVC, polyvinyl chloride; TA, terephthalic acid.

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CBA10055, whereas the mesophilic GEN0105 exhibited higher polyesterase activity. Two ancestral variants of GEN0105 showed higher thermostability and activity against PCL and PLA, but reduced activity with amorphous PET. Furthermore, six established PETases were found to be highly active against PCL and PLA. Thus, our results indicate that polyesterase activity is widespread in the family IV carboxylesterases, and that most polyesterases are promiscuous being able to degrade different polyesters.

1. Introduction

Plastics (polymeric materials) have become ubiquitous in our modern life, and they are used across every sector addressing our numerous needs for materials, construction, transport, packaging, clothing, electronics, and health. Since 1960, global production of plastics has increased 20-fold, reaching 390.7 million tons in 2021, and it is expected to double over the next 20 years (Plastics Europe, Plastics – the Facts 2022). Nearly all plastics are produced from petroleum-based feedstock with almost 9 billion tons of plastics manufactured to date, of which 9 % has been recycled, 12 % has been incinerated, 40 % has been landfilled, whereas up to 39 % is estimated to escape the collection system ending up in diverse natural habitats [1,2]. Synthetic polymers are known to be highly persistent in nature, resulting in the accumulation of plastic waste and causing an environmental pollution crisis [3,4]. Single use plastic products are a major source of plastic leakage into the environment representing up to 50 % of marine litter. Low plastics recycling rates are also associated with huge loss of valuable materials, whereas enormous amounts of petroleum are required each year to provide modern industries with virgin polymers [2,5]. Therefore, we urgently need to establish a circular plastics economy, which will diminish plastic pollution, prevent material loss, and reduce greenhouse gas emissions associated with virgin plastics production [6,7]. The most sustainable approach for plastic waste treatment appears to be a closed-loop recycling process based on physical, chemical, and biocatalytic plastic depolymerization and recovery of chemical feedstocks for the synthesis of novel polymers (a circular economy) [7–9].

The five major plastics types (“big five”) include polypropylene (PP), polyethylene (PE), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polystyrene (PS), and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) [1]. PET is a semi-aromatic synthetic polyester prepared by esterification of ethylene glycol (EG) with terephthalic acid (TA) producing bis(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalate (BHET) followed by BHET polymerization to form low-molecular weight PET (suitable for fibers) and high-molecular weight PET (suitable for drink bottles) [1]. Other semi-aromatic polyesters include poly(trimethylene terephthalate) (PTT), polybutylene terephthalate (PBT), poly(butylene adipate terephthalate) (PBAT), and poly(ethylene naphthalate) (PEN) [10,11]. Due to its durability, good mechanical performance, excellent packaging properties, and low cost, PET is the fourth-most-produced plastic and the most used polyester with numerous applications in fibers, textiles, drink bottles, packaging materials, tapes, and so on. Aliphatic polyesters include poly(lactic acid) (PLA), polycaprolactone (PCL), polyglycolic acid (PGA), poly(ethylene adipate) (PEA), and poly(butylene succinate) (PBS), which have many commodity and specialty applications (fibers, packaging materials, durable goods, disposable cutlery, medicine) [10,11]. Examples of naturally occurring polyesters include cutin (plant polyesters made from C16 and C18 ω -hydroxy-fatty acid monomers cross-linked with glycerol), shellac (a complex mix of several polyesters produced by some insects and composed of aliphatic hydroxyacids and sesquiterpene acids), and poly(hydroxybutyrate) (PHB).

In nature, different groups of aerobic and anaerobic bacteria and fungi have been found to degrade both natural and synthetic polyesters using various hydrolytic enzymes: carboxylesterases (EC 3.1.1.1), lipases (EC 3.1.1.3), cutinases (EC 3.1.1.74), and proteases (EC 3.4.21) [11–14]. All these enzymes are members of the large superfamily of serine-dependent α/β hydrolases, which use the catalytic triad Ser-His-Asp/Glu for the hydrolysis of ester bonds in monoester and

polyester substrates. Enzymatic hydrolysis of synthetic polyesters was demonstrated over 50 years ago using purified proteases (chymotrypsin) and lipases from different fungi and *Achromobacter* sp., as well as hog liver esterase [15,16]. To date, a significant number of polyester-hydrolyzing enzymes (polyesterases) from different bacteria and fungi have been identified using both *in silico* mining and activity-based (naïve) screening with the main focus on PET-degrading enzymes (PETases), including metagenomic LCC (leaf-branch compost cutinase) and IsPETase from *Ideonella sakaiensis* [1,14,17–21]. Recently, a bioinformatic search algorithm based on a Hidden Markov Model (HMM) and nine sequences of known PETases identified 504 possible PET hydrolase genes in existing genome and metagenome databases [17]. Another HMM and machine learning search based on sequences of 17 confirmed PETases revealed 74 putative thermotolerant PETase genes in thermophilic metagenomes and genomes representing seven distinct phylogenetic groups [18]. However, this study suggested that the current sequence-based methods limit the identification of novel PET-degrading enzymes to a narrow sequence space in the vicinity of known PETases [18].

Over the past 10 years, the number of known plastics-degrading enzymes was quickly growing due to high interest in these biocatalysts for plastics recycling applications [1,22,23]. Currently, at least 196 biochemically characterized plastics-active enzymes have been listed in the Plastics-Active Enzymes (PAZy) database, whereas the PlasticDB includes 212 proteins linked to plastics biodegradation [24,25]. Compared to biochemically characterized PETases (93 proteins), smaller numbers of polyesterases active against PLA (38), PBAT (14), PHA (16), and PBS (4) were described to date (72 proteins in the PAZy database) [24,26–30]. In addition, the presence of hydrolytic activity toward PCL, poly(ethylene furanoate) (PEF) and other aliphatic-aromatic polyesters was demonstrated for purified carboxylesterases and cutinases from various bacteria, fungi, and environmental metagenomes [20,26,28,29,31–38]. For some of the purified polyesterases, the hydrolytic activity against soluble chromogenic monoesters (e.g. *p*-nitrophenyl acetate or *p*-nitrophenyl butyrate, common substrates for carboxylesterases) was also characterized [28,37–39]. Crystal structures have been determined for several natural polyesterases, including cutinases (*Humicola insolens* HiC, *Thermobifida alba* Est119, *T. fusca*, and metagenomic LCC) and carboxylesterases (*Clostridium hathewayi* ChathEst1, *C. botulinum* CbotuEstA, *Rhodospseudomonas palustris* RPA1511, and *I. sakaiensis*) [28,40–46]. These structures revealed the classical α/β -hydrolase core domain with or without an α -helical lid domain, usually covering the active site cleft with the catalytic Ser residue at the bottom. The polyesterase active site typically represents a wide-open cleft, directly accessible to polymeric substrates as revealed by the structures of RPA1511, Est119, and IsPETase in complex with substrate analogues (polyethylene glycol or aromatic diester) bound close to the catalytic triad [43,44,46]. Furthermore, narrowing the IsPETase active site using site-directed mutagenesis (to make it more cutinase-like) produced an engineered PETase, which outperformed the wild-type protein in PET degradation, suggesting that polyesterase activity of wild-type proteins can be improved using protein engineering [45]. Subsequently, several protein engineering studies focused on IsPETase, LCC, and PES-H1 produced improved enzyme variants (ThermoPETase, DuraPETase, FAST-PETase, Hot-PETase, LCC-WCCG, LCC-ICCG, PES-H1 L92F/Q94Y, DepoPETase) actively degrading post-consumer PET at various temperatures (between 30°C and 72°C) and pH [47–53]. However, most of the current *in silico* PETase mining and protein engineering efforts have

been focused primarily on IsPETase, LCC, and PES-H1 (which share 49–55 % of sequence identity to each other and belong to the carboxylesterase family V [54]), whereas little attention has been paid to the discovery and engineering of new classes of polyesters degrading PET and other polyesters [18,22,23,55]. Therefore, the identification and characterization of new classes of PETases and other plastics-degrading enzymes are urgently needed for developing new leads for plastics recycling and upcycling [18,22,23,55,56]. Furthermore, there is clearly a need to discover and characterize highly active enzymes for degrading other, biodegradable polyesters (PCL, PLA, PBS, PBAT) as they appear to be not readily biodegradable in natural environments [57,58].

Recently, we have identified and biochemically characterized three novel metagenomic carboxylesterases (IS10, IS11, and IS12) from hydrothermal vents of Ischia with hydrolytic activity against both monoester and polyester substrates, including PET and PLA [27]. Since IS12 (carboxylesterase family IV) exhibited high monoesterase and polyesterase activities, we were keen to examine how these properties in homologous family IV proteins correlate with overall sequence identity to IS12, and if the discovery of novel polyesters can be enhanced using more sensitive high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) assays. In this study, we analyzed monoesterase and polyesterase activities of 26 purified α/β -hydrolases from different metagenomes and bacterial genomes, which belong to the carboxylesterase family IV with sequence identity to IS12 varying from 22 % to 80 %. Substrate screening using spectrophotometric, agarose clearing, and HPLC assays revealed the presence of hydrolytic activity against chromogenic monoester substrates and several polyesters (PET, PCL, and PLA) in all tested proteins. Ancestral sequence reconstruction of the mesophilic metagenomic polyesterase GEN0105 produced two ancestral variants with greatly improved thermostability. Polyesterase activity and stability of several selected enzymes were further characterized along with the two ancestral variants and six known PETases revealing promiscuous hydrolytic activity toward other polyesters.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents

All chemicals and substrates used in this study were of analytical grade and were purchased from Sigma/Aldrich/Merck (Gillingham, UK) and Tokyo Chemical Industry UK Ltd. (TCI, Oxford, UK) including chromogenic *p*-nitrophenyl (pNP) esters (C₂-C₁₈) and polyester substrates poly(D,L-lactide) (PLA, molecular weight M_w range 10,000–18,000), polycaprolactone (PCL, average M_n ~10,000), and amorphous polyethylene terephthalate (PET, thickness 0.25 mm, coil width 600 mm). The model PET substrate bis(benzoyloxyethyl) terephthalate (3PET, M_w 462.4) was synthesized by CanSyn (Toronto, Canada) using a previously reported protocol [59], whereas Impranil® DLN was received as a gift from WhitChem Ltd (UK, produced by Covestro AG).

2.2. Gene cloning and protein purification

The coding sequences of selected hydrolase genes were PCR amplified using the genomic DNA of the host organism or metagenomic fosmids as the templates and cloned into a modified p15TVL expression vector (Novagen) encoding an N-terminal 6His-tag (Table S1). The codon optimized sequences of selected benchmark PETases (IsPETase, HotPETase, FAST-PETase, TfCut1, TfCut2) were commercially synthesized and cloned into a modified p15TVL (Twist Bioscience) based on their Uniprot and published sequences (A0A0K8P6T7 for IsPETase, FAST-PETase, and Hot-PETase; G8GER6 for TfCut1; Q6A0I4 for TfCut2), whereas LCC_WCCG was a gift from Dr. Graeme Howe (Queen's University, Kingston, ON Canada) [48,50,51]. All plasmids were transformed into the *E. coli* BL21(DE3) cells, which were grown in 1 L TB cultures to optical density 0.6–0.8 (600 nm) and induced with 0.4 mM

IPTG (overnight at 16°C). Recombinant proteins were purified to near homogeneity (>95 %, Fig. S1) using nickel-chelate affinity chromatography on Ni-NTA Superflow resin (Qiagen) as described previously [26]. Purity and protein size of purified enzymes were assessed using denaturing polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE), whereas protein concentration was measured by Bradford assay (Merck, Gillingham, UK).

2.3. Carboxylesterase assays with soluble ester substrates

Carboxylesterase activity of purified proteins was measured spectrophotometrically using chromogenic *p*-nitrophenyl (pNP) esters of fatty acids with different acyl chain lengths: pNP-acetate (C2), pNP-butyrate (C4), pNP-hexanoate (C6), pNP-octanoate (C8), pNP-dodecanoate (C12), pNP-myristate (C14), pNP-palmitate (C16), and pNP-stearate (C18) essentially as described previously [20,39]. All assays were conducted in triplicate at indicated temperatures in 96-well plates with reaction mixtures (200 μ l) containing 50 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.0) buffer (or as indicated), 1 mM substrate (C2 to C18), and 1 μ g of enzyme. The reaction mixtures were incubated for 20 min at the indicated temperature, and the activity was calculated based on the absorbance of *p*-nitrophenol at 410 nm ($\epsilon = 17.8 \text{ mM}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$). For determination of kinetic parameters (K_m and k_{cat}), carboxylesterase activity was measured at 30°C over a range of substrate concentrations (0.01 to 2.5 mM), and kinetic parameters were calculated by non-linear regression analysis of raw data fit to the Michaelis-Menten function using R version 4.2.0 (2022-04-22) or GraphPad Prism software (version 5.0). Screening of purified proteins for esterase activity against 96 aromatic and aliphatic esters was performed using a pH-shift based protocol with 0.45 mM Phenol Red as pH indicator in a reaction mixture (44 μ l) containing 5 mM EPPS ((N-2-hydroxyethyl)piperazine-N'-(3-propane sulfonic acid)) buffer (pH 8.0), indicated substrate (1.14 mg/ml) and protein (0.5–1.0 mg/reaction) as described previously [60].

2.4. Enzyme reaction conditions and stability

The effect of pH on carboxylesterase activity of purified proteins (pH profile) was determined using the universal Britton-Robinson buffer system (50 mM acetic acid, 50 mM phosphoric acid, 50 mM boric acid, pH range 3.0 to 10.5) [61]. Temperature optimum for carboxylesterase activity of selected enzymes was measured at temperatures from 30°C to 90°C using 1 mM pNP-ester substrate (C6 or C8) and 0.01–1.0 μ g of protein in 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer (pH 8.0). For the analysis of enzyme thermostability, the selected proteins (1.9–3.6 mg/ml) were incubated for 2 h (or as indicated) at different temperatures (from 30°C to 90°C), and the remaining carboxylesterase activity was measured using 1 mM pNP-ester substrate (C6 or C8). The effect of NaCl and Tween-20 on carboxylesterase activity of selected proteins was analyzed using 1.0 mM pNP-substrate (C6 or C8, as indicated), 1 μ g of enzyme, and 0.1–2.0 M NaCl or 0.01 %–4.5 % Tween-20.

2.5. Thermal denaturation analysis of purified proteins

Comparative analysis of protein thermodenaturation and determination of apparent melting temperatures (T_m) were performed using two methods: differential scanning fluorimetry (DSF) and circular dichroism (CD) spectroscopy. DSF of selected enzymes was carried out on a QuantStudio 6 Flex system (Applied Biosystems, Thermo Fisher Scientific) using SYPRO Orange (Invitrogen) as a reporter dye [62]. Experiments were conducted in triplicate with 30- μ l protein samples (10 μ g of protein) in 50 mM HEPES-K buffer (pH 7.5) containing 50 mM NaCl and 25X SYPRO Orange in sealed optically clear 96-well plates (Applied Biosystems) with the system set on the ROX channel (using the 450/490 nm excitation and 560/580 nm emission filters). The temperatures were increased from 25°C to 95°C (with an increment of 1°C s⁻¹), and T_m values for selected proteins were determined by non-linear fitting of

sigmoidal curves to a Boltzmann equation using the GraphPad Prism software (version 5.0). Protein thermostability was also analyzed by circular dichroism with CD spectra recorded on a JASCO J-8 spectropolarimeter with a constant nitrogen (N_2) flushing as described previously [63]. For each purified protein, the temperatures were varied from 10°C to 95°C, CD spectra were recorded as mean of three independent scans, and T_m values were calculated a Graph Pad Prism 5.0 software and sigmoidal curve fitting.

2.6. Preparation of polyester substrates and polyesterase assays

Several polyester substrates used in this study (PLA, PCL, 3PET, amorphous PET, and Impranil® DLN) were emulsified in 50 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.0) essentially as described previously [26,64,65] and were used both for agarose-based screens and liquid assays. 0.5 g of solid polyesters were dissolved in 4 ml of dichloromethane (or hexafluoroisopropanol for amorphous PET) and using a glass pipette transferred (by drops) to 100 ml of 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer (pH 8.0) supplemented with 40 μ l of Tween-20 with vigorous stirring on a stir plate. For Impranil emulsions (1 %), 1 ml of commercial Impranil® DLN was mixed with 100 ml of 50 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.0). The suspensions were stirred (500 rpm) overnight in a fume hood at room temperature (22°C) for solvent evaporation and sonicated for 10 min at 85 % amplitude (Qsonica sonicator, model Q700).

For agarose-based screens, polyester emulsions (0.5–1 %) were diluted with 2–3 volumes of 2 % agarose and solidified in rectangular cell culture dishes to make a uniformly opaque gel. Enzyme aliquots (20–30 μ l) containing 30–50 μ g of protein were loaded into cylindrical wells punched in the agarose, and sealed plates were incubated at 30°C and monitored for 3–5 days. The formation of a clear zone around the wells was considered as indication for the presence of polyester-degrading (polyesterase) activity [64].

For polyesterase assays in solution and reaction product analysis using HPLC, the reaction mixtures (200 μ l) contained 10–50 μ g of purified protein and 0.125 % of emulsified polyester in 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer (pH 8.0). After 12 h incubation at the indicated temperature (30°C, 60°C, or 70°C), the reactions were terminated by filtering through a 10-kDa spin filter, and the presence of polyester degradation products in filtrates was analyzed using HPLC on a Prominence-I LC-2030C 3D Plus model (Shimadzu, Japan). With PET as substrate (3PET or amorphous PET), the formation of terephthalic acid (TA), mono(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalic acid (MHET), bis(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalic acid (BHET), and benzoic acid (BA) was analyzed using reverse-phase hydrophobic chromatography on a Shimadzu C₁₈ Shim-pack column (150 \times 4.6 mm, 5 μ m particle size) conditioned at 40°C (injection volume 10 μ l, detection at 240 nm). Solvent A was 100 % (v/v) methanol, solvent B was 0.1 % (v/v) orthophosphoric acid (H_3PO_4) in HPLC grade water (flow rate 0.7 ml/min). The elution gradient was: 0–2 min, 25 % A; 2–18 min, linear gradient to 55 % A; 18–22 min, linear gradient to 25 % A. In addition, PET hydrolysis products were analyzed using a Varian Prostar model 330 HPLC systems equipped with a Pursuit 5 C18 column (150 \times 3.9 mm, 5 μ m particle size, Agilent). Solution A was 0.1 % formic acid in water, whereas solution B was 50 % acetonitrile containing 0.1 % formic acid. Elution gradient was as follows: initial 100 % A, 2 min 4 % B, 28 min 85 % B, 29 min 100 % B, 30 min 100 % A, equilibrate 5 min. With PLA or PCL as substrates, the monomeric degradation products lactic acid (LA) and 6-hydroxyhexanoic acid (6-HHA) were detected and quantified using ion-moderated partition chromatography on a Prominence-I LC-2030C 3D Plus HPLC system (Shimadzu, Japan) or on a Varian ProStar HPLC system (model 330) equipped with an Aminex HPX-87-H column (300 \times 7.8 mm, 9 μ m particle size, conditioned at 50°C) and a UV detector (LC-2030C_3Dplus, Shimadzu, Japan). The mobile phase used was 0.05 N sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) in HPLC grade water (flow rate 0.6 ml/min, detection at 210 nm). The hydrolysis products were identified by comparing the retention times with commercial standards and control reactions (without

enzyme or with BSA). All samples were analyzed in triplicate, and the polyester degradation products were quantified based on calibration curves generated using commercially available standards (TA, MHET, BHET, BA, lactic acid, 6-hydroxyhexanoic acid).

2.7. Bioinformatic and structural analyses

Multiple sequence alignments of selected carboxylesterases were performed using the MAFFT online service [66] and modified using the online software STRAP [67]. The phylogenetic tree of selected proteins and benchmark polyesterases was generated using Geneious version 11.0.12 (the Geneious Tree Builder neighbor-joining method with bootstrap of 1000 replicates) (<https://www.geneious.com>).

The Ancestral Sequence Reconstruction (ASR) of GEN0105 was performed using the FireProt ASR v1.1 [68] with homologous sequences (from NCBI GenBank) limited to 150 proteins and the catalytic triad residues of GEN0105 (Ser168, Glu262, and His292) protected from mutations. The resulting phylogenetic tree comprised 141 sequences from Bacteria, six sequences from Archaea, two sequences from Eukaryotes, and one unclassified sequence. From these sequences, two ancestral variants (Node 152 and Node 186) were selected for cloning (gene synthesis) and biochemical characterization.

Structural models of selected polyesterases were constructed using the AlphaFold2-based ColabFold platform for protein folding coupled with Google Colaboratory [69]. The PYMOL Molecular Graphics System (version 1.7.2.1, Schrodinger, LLC) was used for model viewing and preparing structural figures. The best ranked structural models were then used for calculating protein surface electrostatic potential using the PDB2PQR and APBS servers [70,71], whereas the protein surface hydrophobicity was visualized using Chimera X1.4 [72]. The universal toolkit MOLE 2.5.17.4.24 (desktop version) was used for the analysis of tunnels and active sites in the structural models of wild type and reconstructed GEN0105 variants with the probe radius varied from 1 Å to 2 Å [73].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Sequence analysis and carboxylesterase activity of purified α/β hydrolases

In this study, we selected a set of 25 bacterial α/β hydrolases, which share 22–80 % of sequence identity to IS12 and are expressed as soluble proteins in *E. coli* cells (Table S1, Fig. S1). These genes were recovered mostly from mesophilic environmental metagenomes and bacterial genomes (*Alcanivorax borkumensis*, *Cycloclasticus zancles*, *Cytobacillus firmus*; 23 proteins), as well as from thermophilic metagenomes (*Chloroflexota*, 2 proteins) (Table S1). Sequence analysis of these genes revealed no presence of predicted signal peptides suggesting that they are intracellular proteins in host organisms. In the Uniprot database, these sequences are annotated as α/β hydrolases, putative esterases/lipases, or lipolytic enzymes, and the presence of carboxylesterase activity was previously reported for eight of these proteins [26,60,74]. According to the Arpigny-Jaeger classification of lipolytic enzymes [54], IS12 and selected homologous proteins belong to the carboxylesterase family IV (hormone sensitive-like) with the characteristic catalytic Ser motif GDSAGG (Table S1, Fig. S2). Further sequence analysis revealed that the selected proteins form two phylogenetic clusters (subfamilies), IV-1 (14 proteins) and IV-2 (11 proteins), with different sequence motifs near the catalytic Asp and His (IV-1: DPL... HGF; IV-2: LLD... HVF), with the exception of MGS-MesE1 (IV-3), which is positioned between the two protein clusters and has a slightly different His motif (HAF) (Fig. 1, Table S1). Most of the selected proteins showed low or moderate sequence similarity to IS12 (22 % to 60 % amino acid identity), except for CBA10055 (80 % identity) (Table S1, Fig. S2). In addition, there are three other pairs of proteins in the set with highly similar sequences including MGS0008/MGS0017 (80 % identity), MGS0018/MGS0171

Fig. 1. Unrooted phylogenetic tree of 26 family IV carboxylesterases used in this study. The proteins are mostly clustered into two sub-families: IV-1 (14 proteins) and IV-2 (11 proteins) with MGS-MesE1 (IV-3) positioned separately (the tree scale is 0.1). The tree also shows four pairs of proteins with high sequence identity: IS12/CBA10055 (80 % sequence identity), MGS0008/MGS0017 (80 %), MGS0018/MGS0171 (90 %), and CF114619/PTH04245 (78 %).

(90 %), and CF114619/PTH04245 (78 %) (Fig. 1). Based on protein sequence, IS12 and 10 selected proteins from the subfamily IV-1 (BHR01264, CBA10055, CBA17115, CF114619, Lip9a, MGS0004, MGS0090, MGS0103, MGS-MesE1, and PTH04245) are also related to the recently proposed phylogenetic group-1 of thermotolerant PETases [18], but the other proteins (ANB01465, BHR00087, GEN0093, MGS0077 and all proteins from the subfamily-2) showed no clustering with any of the seven proposed PETase groups (Table S1).

The selected α/β hydrolase genes (Table S1) were over-expressed in *E. coli*, and affinity purified proteins (Fig. S1) were screened for carboxylesterase activity at 30°C using a range of chromogenic *p*-nitrophenyl (pNP)-esters with different acyl chain lengths (C2-C18) (Fig. 2). These screens revealed the presence of carboxylesterase activity in all purified proteins, with high activity observed in IS12, CBA10055, CBA17115, CF114619, GEN0093, GEN0105, and MGS-MesE1 (Fig. 2). The tested enzymes showed the highest activity toward C2 and C4 substrates and low activity against long acyl chain esters (C16 and C18) suggesting that these enzymes are genuine carboxylesterases (Fig. 2).

3.2. Polyesterase activity of purified carboxylesterases against different polyesters

The presence of hydrolytic (polyesterase) activity against synthetic polyesters in purified selected proteins was analyzed using both agarose clearing screens (indicator plates) and HPLC product analysis with emulsified PET, PCL, PLA, and Impranil DLN (an aliphatic polyester-polyurethane colloid, [75]) as substrates (Figs. 3, 4, S3). Based on agarose clearing assays, IS12 and 14 other proteins showed positive results for polyesterase activity against the short-chain model PET substrate bis(benzoyloxyethyl) terephthalate (3PET) (Figs. 3, 4), which has been shown to correlate with hydrolytic activity on PET-films [59,76]. In these screens, high hydrolytic activity against 3PET was observed for

GEN0105, MAGIC0005, MGS-MesE1, and MGS0103, whereas eight proteins (IS12, BHR0087, CBA10055, GEN0093, Lip9a, MGS0018, MGS0077, and MGS0171) showed lower activity, and 11 proteins appeared to be inactive (Figs. 3, 4). Similarly, CBA10055, GEN0105, and MGS0171 showed high hydrolytic activity in agarose-clearing screens with PCL (average $M_w \sim 14,000$) as substrate with 15 other proteins showing prominent or detectable activity (Figs. 3, 4). Finally, three proteins were found to be positive in agarose-clearing screens with PLA (poly(D,L-lactide), M_w range 10,000–18,000) as substrate (IS12, CBA10055, and GEN0105), whereas four proteins showed hydrolytic activity against the polyester-polyurethane substrate Impranil DLN (CBA10055, GEN0105, MGS0018, and MGS0171) (Figs. 3, 4).

Purified α/β -hydrolases were also analyzed for the presence of polyesterase activity against 3PET, PCL, and PLA using HPLC for the detection of soluble reaction products (Fig. 4). During PET hydrolysis, the biochemically characterized PET-degrading enzymes have been shown to produce a variable mix of aromatic reaction products (and ethylene glycol) including terephthalic acid (TA), mono(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalate (MHET), and bis(2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalate (BHET), whereas with 3PET as substrate they also produce benzoic acid (BA) and 2-hydroxyethyl benzoate (HEB) as products [14, 77–81]. Remarkably, all purified proteins showed detectable or significant polyesterase activity against emulsified 3PET with the highest hydrolytic activity observed in GEN0105 (Fig. 4, S3). All tested proteins produced MHET and BA as the primary reaction products, whereas seven enzymes (IS12, BHR0087, CBA10055, CF114619, MAGIC0005, MGS0018, and MGS0103) also formed detectable amounts of BHET (but no TA) (Fig. 4). Moreover, three proteins (GEN0105, MGS-MesE1, and MGS0089) generated significant amounts of TA as an additional product suggesting that they can hydrolyze MHET (Fig. 4). As reported previously, 3PET can also be used to distinguish between the endo- and exo-cleavage of polyester substrates based on the analysis of reaction

Fig. 2. Screening of 26 purified α/β -hydrolases for carboxylesterase activity using chromogenic pNP-esters with different acyl chain lengths. Purified proteins (1 μg /reaction) were incubated at 30°C (20 min) in a reaction mixture containing 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer (pH 8.0) and indicated substrates (1 mM, C2-C18). All assays were carried out in triplicate, and results are means from at least two independent determinations. n.d., not detectable (below the limit of detection, <0.01 U/mg).

products [76,78,79]. Since all tested proteins produced MHET and BA as products, they appear to catalyze mainly the exo-cleavage of 3PET followed by the hydrolysis of 3PET-derived degradation products BHET and MHET (Fig. 4, S3).

Furthermore, HPLC analysis of reaction products after incubation of purified enzymes with emulsified PCL (average M_w 14,000) as substrate revealed the formation of 6-hydroxyhexanoic acid (6-HHA) in all tested proteins with the highest polyesterase activity observed in GEN0105 and CBA10055 (Fig. 4). Similarly, all purified proteins (except CFI14619) produced detectable or significant amounts of monomeric lactic acid as soluble product after incubation with emulsified PLA (poly(D,L-lactide), M_w 10,000–18,000) as substrate (Fig. 4). In these screens, the highest polyesterase activity was observed in CBA10055 (both with PCL and PLA) and GEN0105 (with PCL) (Fig. 4). Based on our previous studies with PLA-degrading enzymes [26,44], the tested enzymes are also expected to produce oligomeric products (dimers, trimers, and higher oligomers) during PCL and PLA degradation.

Thus, HPLC-based assays with emulsified 3PET, PCL, and PLA as substrates demonstrated the presence of polyesterase activity in all 26 family IV carboxylesterases with most proteins being active against the three tested polyesters. Therefore, the agarose-clearing screens for polyesterase activity with emulsified polyesters appear to have a lower

sensitivity as they were able to detect polyesterase activity only in several highly active enzymes (e.g. GEN0105 and CBA10055 from this study). Nonetheless, the indicator plate screens revealed the presence of polyesterase activity in approximately 17 % of purified α/β hydrolases (36 positives from 213 screened) in our previous study [26]. The presence of polyesterase activity in many microbial carboxylesterases is consistent with the current view that polyesterase (PETase) activity of carboxylesterases represents a promiscuous activity of these enzymes [11,82]. From our set of 26 carboxylesterases (Table S1), eight proteins were previously screened against a library of 96 soluble monoesters and showed high (GEN0093, MGS0077, MGS0090, MGS0103) or low (ABO2108, MGS0017, MGS0018, MGS0089) substrate promiscuity with these substrates [60,74]. The results of the present study (Figs. 2, 4) suggest that high substrate promiscuity of carboxylesterases toward monoester substrates appears to show no correlation with high polyesterase activity of these enzymes.

3.3. Structural analysis of four selected polyesterases

Based on substrate screening results (Figs. 2, 4), the four most active polyesterases with a broad substrate range were selected for a more detailed biochemical analysis including GEN0105 (subfamily IV-2),

Fig. 3. Agarose-based screening of purified proteins for polyesterase activity against four different polyesters. The presence of polyesterase activity is indicated by the formation of a clear zone around the wells loaded with indicated proteins (45 $\mu\text{g}/\text{well}$, 72 h at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). The wells labelled “-VE” represent negative controls (no protein).

CBA10055 (IV-1), MGS-MesE1 (IV-3), and BHR01264 (IV-1). The selected enzymes share different levels of sequence similarity to IS12 ranging from 25–26 % sequence identity (GEN0105 and MGS-MesE1) to 65 % (BHR01264) and to 80 % (CBA10055) (Table S1), whereas their sequences showed no significant sequence similarity to IsPETase and

LCC (carboxylesterase family V).

To provide structural insights into the active sites of selected polyesterases, high quality structural models of these enzymes were constructed using the AlphaFold2 server (the ColabFold implementation [83]). The structural models revealed largely similar core domains with a

Fig. 4. Polyesterase activity of 26 purified carboxylesterases as revealed by indicator plate screens and HPLC product analyses. The representative indicator plate (agarose clearing) screens are shown in Fig. 3, and the results are categorized (the Gel column) as: (+++), high activity (large clear halo, >1 cm); (++) , medium activity (medium clear halo, <1 cm); (+), low activity (small/weak clear halo), (-), no detectable activity (no visible clear zone). HPLC-based assays contained the purified protein (10–50 μ g/reaction) and indicated emulsified polyester substrates (representative HPLC chromatograms with 3PET as substrate are shown in Fig. S3). Other experimental conditions were as described in Materials and Methods with all experiments carried out in triplicate, and results are means from at least two independent determinations. n.d., not detectable (below the limit of detection).

classical α/β -hydrolase fold containing a twisted β -sheet (with 8–9 mixed β -strands) flanked by 8–9 α -helices (Fig. S4). The structural model of GEN0105 revealed the presence of an additional β -strand, which includes the N-terminal residues (Met1-Asp19) and is absent in the other three polyesterases. The protein core structures are covered by a small lid domain, which includes the N-terminal residues (20/64 aa for GEN0105 and 1/43–46 aa for other proteins) containing two or three α -helices (Fig. S4). The all-helical lid domains are positioned above the enzyme active site with the catalytic Ser nucleophile located on the canonical nucleophilic elbow (a short sharp turn between the β 5 strand and the following α -helix) (Fig. 5, S4). The active sites also revealed the other two residues of a classical Ser catalytic triad, His and Asp (Glu in GEN0105), located near the nucleophilic Ser, as well as various hydrophobic and polar residues potentially involved in substrate binding (Fig. 5). The GEN0105 active site revealed the presence of six aromatic residues (Tyr96, Phe104, Tyr110, Phe198, Phe201, and Phe218) located in the acyl- and alcohol-binding pockets, whereas the other three enzymes contained three aromatic residues each (Fig. 5). The active site of GEN0105 appears to be more open, and its catalytic triad is placed closer

to the protein surface than in other polyesterases. Protein surface analysis revealed more positively charged residues around the GEN0105 active site compared to other selected polyesterases, from which MGS-MesE1 showed the highest negative surface charge density (Fig. S5). However, surface hydrophobicity analysis showed similar distribution of hydrophilic and hydrophobic patches in the polyesterases with a slightly higher level of hydrophobicity observed around the GEN0105 active site (Fig. S6).

3.4. Polyesterase activity of purified enzymes as a function of reaction conditions

A recent study highlighted the importance of reaction conditions for catalytic performance of polyester (PET) hydrolyzing enzymes [80]. The selected polyesterases were found to be active within a broad range of pH (5.0–10.0) with the highest activity observed at pH 7.5–8.0 (CBA10055 and MGS-MesE1) or pH 8.0–10.0 (BHR01264 and GEN0105) (measured at 30°C with pNP-esters as substrates) (Fig. S7). Both CBA10055 and MGS-MesE1 showed reduced activity at pH

Fig. 5. Structural analysis of selected polyesterses: close-up view of the active sites. Structural models of BHR01264 (A), CBA10055 (B), GEN0105 (C), and MGS-MesE1 (D) were generated using the AlphaFold2 tool [69]. The proteins are presented as ribbon diagrams colored grey with the active site residues shown as sticks with green-colored carbons and the catalytic triad (Ser-His-Asp) labelled in bold and connected by dashed lines.

9.5–10.0, whereas BHR01264 and GEN0105 were more alkali tolerant and retained the maximal activity at these pH values (Fig. S7). The temperature dependence of selected enzymes revealed different activity profiles for *p*NP-ester hydrolysis with GEN0105 and MGS-MesE1 being most active at 50°C and showing reduced activities at higher temperatures (Fig. 6). In contrast, BHR01264 was most active at 70°C, whereas the carboxylesterase activity of CBA10055 was steadily increasing from 30°C to 80°C but declined to low levels at 90°C (Fig. 6). At pH 8.0, carboxylesterase activity of GEN0105 was stimulated (up to 40 %) in the presence of 0.1 M NaCl in the reaction mixture and then gradually decreased at higher NaCl concentrations (up to 2 M) (Fig. S7). The other three enzymes showed a steady decrease of activity in the presence of 0.1 M to 2 M NaCl (Fig. S7). Similarly, most of the characterized carboxylesterases were active over a broad pH range (pH 6–10) and were inhibited by high NaCl concentrations (> 0.1 M) [26,39,84]. In contrast, the addition of the non-ionic detergent Tween 20 had a stimulating effect on esterase activity of four enzymes with an increase in activity ranging from 40 % (BHR01264), to 5–8 times (CBA10055 and GEN0105), and to 30–35 times for MGS-MesE1 (Fig. S7). Interestingly, the carboxylesterase activity of MGS-MesE1 increased only 3.5 times in the presence of another non-ionic detergent, Triton X-100 (0.1–0.5 %, data not shown). Previous research with various non-ionic detergents (Tween and Triton X-100) reported mostly inhibiting effects on purified carboxylesterases and PETases, but several studies also demonstrated low or significant stimulation of activity (up to 250 %) [26,38,39,76,85] (also BRENDA database). Under optimal reaction conditions, the purified polyesterses demonstrated saturation kinetics with chromogenic *p*NP-esters and revealed high substrate affinity (low K_M) and catalytic efficiency (k_{cat}/K_M) toward the tested medium chain-length substrates (C6–C12) (Table 1). In addition, these enzymes showed promiscuous esterase activity against a broad range of soluble ester substrates with 77 positive substrates for MGS-MesE1, as well as many substrates for BHR01264 (60), CBA10055 (43) and GEN0105 (20) (Fig. S8). Therefore, the selected polyesterses exhibit both high (MGS-MesE1, BHR01264, CBA10055) and moderate (GEN0105) substrate promiscuity with

soluble ester substrates.

Thus, the observed activity responses of selected polyesterses to reaction conditions (pH, temperature, NaCl, Tween 20) revealed low similarity to those of IS12 [27]. For example, CBA10055 (80 % identity to IS12) had a similar temperature profile, but different pH optimum and effects of NaCl and Tween 20, whereas BHR01264 (65 % identity to IS12) showed similar effect of pH and NaCl, but different responses to Tween 20 and high temperature (Fig. 6, S7). Therefore, purified carboxylesterases can display different activity responses to reaction conditions even at 80 % of sequence identity.

3.5. Thermostability of purified polyesterses

The thermostability of purified polyesterses was characterized by the analysis of remaining enzyme activity after preincubation at different temperatures and by determining protein melting temperatures (T_m) using differential scanning fluorimetry (DSF). As shown in Fig. 7, after one hour pre-incubation of protein solutions (2.0–3.6 mg/ml) at 30°C, the selected polyesterses retained 60–90 % of initial activity (determined at 30°C). BHR01264 and MGS-MesE1 exhibited no or low activity after 1 h pre-incubation at 40°C, GEN0105 showed reduced (50 %) activity, whereas CBA10066 revealed a small increase (25 %) in activity, which is likely to be due to re-folding of soluble misfolded protein molecules [86] (Fig. 7). After 1 h pre-incubation at 50°C, GEN0105 lost almost all activity, but CBA10055 retained full activity up to 80°C but was inactive after pre-incubation at 90°C (Fig. 7). Since the thermostability of CBA10055 was comparable to that reported recently for IS12 [27], the remaining activity of both enzymes was followed side by side during incubation at 70°C and 80°C in a separate experiment. As shown in Fig. S9, CBA10055 was more thermostable than IS12 and retained full activity after two hours of preincubation at both temperatures. Thus, in agreement with their temperature profiles, the selected polyesterses exhibited low (BHR01264, GEN0105, and MGS-MesE1) or high (CBA10055) thermal tolerance based on remaining activity with the highest thermostability observed in CBA10055.

Fig. 6. Effect of assay temperature on carboxylesterase activity of purified polyesterses. The reaction mixtures (0.2 ml, 1 μ g of enzyme) were incubated at the indicated temperatures for 20 min, and produced *p*-nitrophenol was measured at 410 nm. As substrates, 1 mM *p*NP-hexanoate was used for BHR01264, CBA10055, and Node152, whereas 1 mM *p*NP-octanoate was used for GEN0105, MGS-MesE1, and Node186.

Furthermore, the thermostability of selected polyesterses was characterized based on protein unfolding in the presence of SYPRO Orange as a reporter dye using the differential scanning fluorimetry (DSF) method (see Materials and Methods for details). DSF uses a hydrophobic fluorescence dye to monitor protein denaturation as a function of temperature and determine protein melting temperatures (denaturation midpoint, T_m) [87]. In this study, the melting temperatures of purified polyesterses were determined using DSF along with IsPETase (T_m 46.8°C) and HotPETase, a recently engineered thermostable variant of IsPETase (T_m 82.5°C) [51,88]. In our DSF experiments, the purified IsPETase and HotPETase were found to have T_m 47.8–49.2°C and 82.0–82.3°C, respectively (in the presence of 0.05 M, 0.1 M, and 0.5 M NaCl) (Table S2), which are in good agreement with the previously reported data [51,88]. However, the melting temperatures could not be measured for BHR01264 and MGS-MesE1 due to high fluorescence background at low temperatures and non-ideal denaturation profiles. As expected, the thermostability of GEN0105 (T_m = 43.7°C) was slightly increased at higher NaCl concentrations (T_m = 43.7°C at 0.05 M NaCl vs T_m = 56.8°C at 0.5 M NaCl), but still it was

significantly lower than that of IS12 (T_m = 77.7°C) and CBA10055 (T_m = 91.9°C) (Table 1). Interestingly, CBA1005 (T_m = 91.9°C) was found to be more thermostable compared to HotPETase (T_m 82.3°C), which was engineered from IsPETase using directed enzyme evolution with selection for more active and thermostable PET-hydrolyzing variants [51]. Altogether, the results of enzyme activity temperature profiling show good correlation with the activity-based thermostability analysis and protein melting temperatures and identify CBA10055 as a highly thermostable polyesterase.

3.6. Ancestral sequence reconstruction of GEN0105 and biochemical characterization of two ancestral variants

In this study, the metagenomic esterase GEN0105 was identified as one of the most active and promiscuous polyesterses compared to other tested proteins (Figs. 1–4). However, purified GEN0105 exhibited rather lower thermostability retaining only 50 % of initial activity after one hour incubation at 40 °C (T_m = 42.7°C compared to 77.7°C for IS12) (Table 1). Recent studies on ancestral sequence reconstruction (ASR) of

Table 1
Kinetic parameters^a and melting temperatures (T_m)^b of purified polyesterses.

Protein	Substrate	K_M mM	k_{cat} s^{-1}	k_{cat}/K_M $s^{-1} M^{-1}$	T_m °C
1. IS12 ^c	pNP-butyrate	0.08 ± 0.01	8.8 ± 0.3	1.1 × 10 ⁵	77.7
	pNP-hexanoate	0.09 ± 0.01	19.1 ± 0.5	2.1 × 10 ⁵	
2. BHR01264	pNP-hexanoate	0.06 ± 0.01	0.10 ± 0.01	1.6 × 10 ³	n.m. ^d (73.9)
	pNP-octanoate	0.9 ± 0.6	2.7 ± 0.7	0.3 × 10 ⁴	
3. CBA10055	pNP-hexanoate	0.8 ± 0.2	37.0 ± 4.0	0.5 × 10 ⁵	91.9 (89.7)
	pNP-octanoate	0.01 ± 0.003	0.9 ± 0.1	0.6 × 10 ⁵	
	pNP-dodecanoate	0.05 ± 0.01	0.9 ± 0.1	1.5 × 10 ⁴	
4. MGS-MesE1	pNP-hexanoate	1.3 ± 0.7	2.4 ± 0.6	1.8 × 10 ²	n.m. (43.3)
	pNP-octanoate	0.10 ± 0.05	14.7 ± 1.6	1.0 × 10 ⁵	
	pNP-dodecanoate	2.8 ± 1.0	55.2 ± 12.5	2.0 × 10 ⁴	
5. GEN0105	pNP-hexanoate	0.9 ± 0.2	7.0 ± 0.7	0.8 × 10 ⁴	43.7 (54.0)
	pNP-octanoate	0.8 ± 0.1	6.6 ± 0.4	0.9 × 10 ⁴	
	pNP-dodecanoate	1.3 ± 0.4	1.0 ± 0.1	0.7 × 10 ³	
6. Node152	pNP-hexanoate	0.7 ± 0.4	0.8 ± 0.1	1.1 × 10 ³	52.0
	pNP-octanoate	0.14 ± 0.05	0.80 ± 0.05	0.6 × 10 ⁴	
7. Node186	pNP-hexanoate	0.55 ± 0.28	8.8 ± 1.6	1.6 × 10 ⁴	64.7
	pNP-octanoate	0.64 ± 0.21	7.4 ± 0.4	1.2 × 10 ⁴	
	pNP-dodecanoate	0.08 ± 0.06	0.4 ± 0.1	0.5 × 10 ⁴	

^a Determined with indicated substrates at 30 °C.

^b Determined using differential scanning fluorimetry (DSF) and circular dichroism (CD) spectroscopy (values shown in brackets).

^c The kinetic parameters of IS12 are from Distaso et al., 2023 [26], whereas T_m is from this work.

^d n.m., not measurable (poor quality melting curves).

Fig. 7. Thermostability of selected polyesterses: activity-based analysis. Following 1 h pre-incubation at different temperatures (from 30°C to 90°C), the remaining carboxylesterase activity of purified proteins was measured at 30°C using soluble chromogenic substrates as a function of pre-incubation temperature (from 30°C to 90°C). Enzyme solutions (BHR01264: 2.0 mg/ml, CBA10055: 3.3 mg/ml, GEN0105: 2.3 mg/ml, MGS-MesE1: 3.6 mg/ml) were pre-incubated at indicated temperatures for 1 h, and the remaining carboxylesterase activity was measured at 30°C with 1 mM pNP-octanoate as substrate (1.5 µg of protein/reaction). The relative activity for each pre-incubation temperature was calculated by comparing the remaining enzyme activity at 30°C to that of the freshly thawed enzyme. n.d., not detectable (below the limit of detection).

several enzymes have demonstrated increased thermostability and diversified substrate specificity in ancestral proteins [89–91]. Therefore, we used ASR to reconstruct functional ancestors of GEN0105 with the goal of identifying more thermostable variants with polyesterase

activity. This approach involves assessing amino acid conservation using multiple sequence alignments of proteins homologous to GEN0105 and reconstructing ancestral sequences using an evolutionary matrix. As a result, the GEN0105 phylogenetic tree comprised 141 sequences from Bacteria, six sequences from Archaea, two sequences from Eukaryotes, and one unclassified sequence (Fig. 8A). The ASR analysis based on this tree revealed 150 sequences of possible GEN0105 ancestors, from which we selected two variants positioned near (Node186) and distantly (Node152) to GEN0105 for biochemical analysis (Fig. 8A). The ancestral variants Node152 and Node186 share 42 % and 52 % sequence identity to GEN0105, respectively (36–37 % to IS12) (Fig. S10, Table S1, S3). In addition, they show 46 % to 58 % sequence identity to biochemically characterized metagenomic carboxylesterases EstD11 and E40, which have not yet been tested with polyester substrates [84,92].

Both Node152 and Node186 genes were recombinantly expressed in *E. coli* cells, and the presence of carboxylesterase activity in the purified proteins was confirmed using pNP-esters as substrates (Fig. 8B, Table 1). With pNP-esters, Node186 showed hydrolytic activity similar or slightly higher than that of GEN0105, whereas the Node152 activity was approximately two times lower (Fig. 8B, Table 1). Analysis of kinetic parameters revealed similar substrate affinities (K_M) and turnover numbers (k_{cat}) with pNP-esters for Node186 and GEN0105, whereas Node152 showed lower k_{cat} with C6 and C8 substrates resulting in lower catalytic efficiency (k_{cat}/K_M) (Table 1). Activity-based thermostability analysis of purified enzymes demonstrated greatly enhanced thermostability in both Node152 and Node186 compared to GEN0105 with the ancestral variants retaining 50–60 % of initial activity after 1 h incubation at 60°C and 70°C (Fig. 8C). Likewise, DSF experiments identified significantly higher melting temperatures (T_m) for both ancestral variants (52.0 °C and 64.7 °C) compared to GEN0105 (43.7 °C) (Table 1).

Similar to GEN0105, the structural models of Node152 and Node186 prepared using the AlphaFold2 server [69] revealed a classical α/β -hydrolase fold with a small α -helical lid domain (Fig. S4). In contrast to GEN0105, the models of Node152 and Node186 showed no presence of the additional N-terminal β -strand with the central β -sheet containing eight β -strands (like in other polyesterses from this study) (Fig. S4). Like in GEN0105, the catalytic Ser triad of Node152 and Node186 included the conserved residues Ser149-His273-Glu243 and Ser159-His283-Glu253, respectively, as well as a large number of hydrophobic amino acids (Fig. 9). Structural analysis of surface charge and hydrophobicity distribution revealed the dominance of positively

Fig. 8. Ancestral sequence reconstruction of GEN0105. (A), The phylogenetic tree used for the ancestral sequence reconstruction of GEN0105 (indicated by the blue star) with two selected ancestral variants (Node152 and Node186) indicated by red stars. (B), Carboxylesterase activity and (C) thermostability of purified GEN0105 and two ancestral variants. Carboxylesterase activity of purified proteins was measured at 30°C using 1 mM *p*NP-octanoate as substrate, whereas their thermostability was determined as remaining activity after 1 h pre-incubation at indicated temperatures (C).

charged residues around the active site openings in Node152 and Node186 compared to GEN0105 and other polyesterases from this study, whereas surface hydrophobicity of these proteins appeared to be similar (Fig. S11). Based on the analysis of protein tunnels and active site cavities (using the MOLE 2.5 software), Node152 possessed the longer tunnel connecting the catalytic Ser with protein surface and larger active site volume compared to Node186 and GEN0105, which however showed higher hydrolytic activity toward *p*NP-esters (Fig. 9, Table S4, S5). In line with previous observations [93], higher thermostability observed in both ancestral variants correlated with a higher number of

calculated hydrogen bonds in Node152 (2842) and Node186 (2200) compared to GEN0105 (1701), as well as with a higher surface polarity (Fig. S11). Thus, ancestral sequence reconstruction of GEN0105 identified two protein variants with carboxylesterase activity and greatly improved thermostability, which were selected for comparative analysis of polyester-degrading activity.

Fig. 9. Ancestral sequence reconstruction of GEN0105: close-up view of the active sites and substrate access tunnels of GEN0105 and two ancestral variants. Structural models of GEN0105 (A), Node152 (B), and Node186 (C) were generated using the AlphaFold2 tool (ref 83). The proteins are presented as ribbon diagrams colored grey with the active site residues indicated as sticks with green-colored carbons and the catalytic triad (Ser-His-Asp) marked in bold. The right-side panels (D, E, F) show cut-away views of substrate access tunnels connecting the catalytic Ser to the protein surface in GEN0105 (D), Node152 (E), and Node186 (F). The protein monomers are shown in surface representation with electrostatic potential clipped using the same clipping planes, and the substrate access tunnels are visualized as a set of intersecting spheres (colored pink).

3.7. Hydrolytic activity of novel polyesters and known PETases against PET, PCL, and PLA

The presence of polyesterase activity in purified ancestral proteins Node152 and Node186 was investigated using emulsified polyesters (amorphous PET, PCL, and PLA) as substrates and HPLC for the detection of soluble reaction products (Table 2). The experiments were performed at three different temperatures (30°C, 60°C, and 70°C) along with GEN0105, CBA10055, and IS12, as well as with the wild type and two engineered variants of IsPETase (HotPETase and FastPETase), the engineered leaf-branch compost cutinase LCC_WCCG, and two *T. fusca* cutinases (TfCut1 and TfCut2) [14,45,50,51] (Table 2, Fig. S12). In these assays, both Node152 and Node186 showed the presence of very low hydrolytic activity against amorphous PET, though GEN0105 produced detectable amounts of MHET and TA at 60°C and 70°C, suggesting a

distinct substrate specificity in both ancestral variants (Table 2). Furthermore, the thermostable polyesterases CBA10055 and IS12 showed undetectable or negligible hydrolytic activity against amorphous PET at three tested temperatures indicating that 3PET-degrading activity appears to show no strict correlation with activity toward amorphous PET. As expected, the benchmark PETases including IsPETase, HotPETase, FastPETase, LCC_WCCG, TfCut1, and TfCut2 demonstrated significant production of both MHET and TA from amorphous PET at three temperatures used with HotPETase and LCC_WCCG showing the highest production of TA (Table 2).

With PCL as substrate, both Node152 and Node186 produced significant amounts of 6-hydroxyhexanoic acid (6-HHA) as product with Node152 being more active compared to Node186 and GEN0105 (Table 2). These results also suggest that the level of carboxylesterase activity of purified proteins against monoesters shows no strict

Table 2Polyester-degrading activity of purified polyesters: HPLC analysis of soluble products^a.

Proteins	Substrate: amorphous PET (products: MHET and TA, mM)					
	30 °C		60 °C		70 °C	
	MHET	TA	MHET	TA	MHET	TA
Node152	0.001	0.001	0.004	0.002	0.004	0.003
Node186	0.001	0.001	0.006	0.001	n.d.	0.001
GEN0105	0.037	0.004	0.084	0.026	0.003	0.018
CBA10055	n.d. ^b	n.d.	0.03	0.03	0.02	n.d.
IS12	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
IsPETase	0.35	1.21	0.44	0.62	0.46	0.67
	± 0.02	± 0.02	± 0.02	± 0.01	± 0.01	± 0.01
HotPETase	n.d.	1.34	n.d.	1.34	n.d.	1.44
		± 0.02		± 0.02		± 0.02
FastPETase	n.d.	1.23	0.49	0.96	0.55	1.17
		± 0.01	± 0.01	± 0.01	± 0.01	± 0.01
LCC_WCCG	0.44	0.16	0.35	1.50	0.13	1.54
	± 0.11	± 0.05	± 0.18	± 0.10	± 0.22	± 0.22
TfCut1	0.51	0.14	0.51	0.45	0.02	0.04
	± 0.02	± 0.01	± 0.21	± 0.02	± 0.02	± 0.01
TfCut2	0.16	0.19	0.18	0.91	n.d.	0.03
	± 0.01	± 0.02	± 0.12	± 0.22		± 0.01
Proteins	Substrate: PCL (product: 6-HHA, mM)			Substrate: PLA (product: LA, mM)		
	30 °C	60 °C	70 °C	30 °C	60 °C	70 °C
Node152	0.37	5.13	3.77	0.97	11.9	15.8
	± 0.08	± 0.27	± 0.79	± 0.15	± 1.4	± 2.8
Node186	0.33	1.08	0.60	n.d.	1.45	1.99
	± 0.01	± 0.02	± 0.07		± 0.23	± 0.09
GEN0105	0.50	4.78	2.14	n.d.	1.12	0.62
	± 0.07	± 0.41	± 0.44		± 0.09	± 0.09
CBA10055	0.47	0.55	0.49	0.02	0.54	0.49
	± 0.01	± 0.01	± 0.04	± 0.003	± 0.08	± 0.10
IS12	0.83	2.02	2.12	0.90	1.38	2.33
	± 0.60	± 0.22	± 0.52	± 0.9	± 0.42	± 0.44
IsPETase	17.0	10.3	8.32	0.15	0.67	0.49
	± 1.1	± 0.6	± 0.53	± 0.04	± 0.22	± 0.09
HotPETase	13.8	13.2	15.9	0.03	1.09	0.72
	± 2.5	± 0.2	± 0.7	± 0.01	± 0.28	± 0.05
FastPETase	12.5	19.6	13.8	0.08	0.39	0.47
	± 0.6	± 0.1	± 1.4	± 0.01	± 0.08	± 0.03
LCC_WCCG	11.48	12.30	12.33	8.72	14.05	15.76
	± 0.33	± 0.91	± 0.76	± 0.47	± 0.65	± 1.34
TfCut1	11.48	11.59	4.16	1.78	4.07	1.62
	± 0.65	± 1.89	± 1.41	± 0.21	± 0.57	± 0.19
TfCut2	11.55	12.44	9.85	0.82	1.39	0.78
	± 0.12	± 0.89	± 0.62	± 0.29	± 0.08	± 0.31

^a Soluble products: 6-hydroxyhexanoic acid (6-HHA), lactic acid (LA), mono (2-hydroxyethyl) terephthalate (MHET), and terephthalic acid (TA).

^b n.d., not detectable.

correlation with their polyesterase activity. Both CBA10055 and IS12 degraded PCL, but their activity was much lower compared to Node152 (Table 2). Finally, the biochemically characterized benchmark PETases (IsPETase, HotPETase, FastPETase, LCC_WCCG, TfCut1, and TfCut2) were found to be highly active with PCL and produced 2–4 times more 6-HHA compared to Node152 (Table 2, Fig. S13). These enzymes were also active with PLA as substrate suggesting that they are not strictly specific to PET and can also be used for the depolymerization of other polyesters. Node152 was found to be 30 times more active in degrading PLA at 70 °C and twice as active against PCL compared to GEN0105 (Table 2), indicating the potential of ASR for improving polyesterase activity. Furthermore, Node152 and LCC_WCCG were the most active PLA-degrading polyesterases with significant activity also observed in several other tested enzymes (Table 2, Fig. S12). Thus, the identified novel polyesterases and several known PET-degrading hydrolases (annotated as PETases) exhibit a broad substrate range and can depolymerize multiple polyesters with aliphatic and aromatic backbones. These results are in line with our previous study demonstrating

hydrolytic activity of purified metagenomic polyesterases against several polyesters (PLA, PCL, 3PET, PES, PBSA) [26].

4. Conclusions

It is still discussed whether the polyester (PET) degrading activity of carboxylesterases is the result of evolution or it represents a promiscuous activity of natural enzymes hydrolyzing natural polyesters (cutinases) or monoesters (carboxylesterases) [55,82]. In this study with 27 family IV carboxylesterases, HPLC assays with purified proteins demonstrated the presence of polyesterase activity against 3PET, PCL, and PLA in all tested proteins suggesting that polyesterase activity is common in the family IV enzymes, and that it likely represents promiscuous activity of these enzymes. Previously, hydrolytic activities with monoester substrates have been reported for several family IV carboxylesterases (e.g. for *Pyrobaculum calidifontis* and metagenomic Est06 and EstD11), but these enzymes were not tested against polyesters [92,94,95]. The proteins analyzed in this study share from 20 % to 80 % of overall sequence identity to the thermophilic family IV polyesterase IS12, which was active against 3PET, PLA, and PCL (Table 2, Fig. S12) [27]. Our results indicate that even at 60 %–80 % sequence identity the tested enzymes exhibit different polyester substrate preference and 3PET product profiles (Figs. 3, 4). In addition, the six established PETases from the carboxylesterase family V (IsPETase, HotPETase, FastPETase, TfCut1, and TfCut2, and LCC_WCCG) have been shown to be highly active against both PCL and PLA (Table 2, Fig. S12) suggesting that natural and engineered PETases can be used for the depolymerization of multiple polyesters. We also confirm that the thermostability of mesophilic enzymes with high polyesterase activity can be enhanced without loss of activity using ancestral sequence reconstruction. Our results suggest that, like bacterial monoesterases [60], many polyesterases from family IV and known PETases from family V exhibit high substrate promiscuity and can degrade several different polyesters. Thus, further research with uncharacterized enzymes from under-investigated carboxylesterase families (including other family IV and beta-lactamase-like esterases) will identify novel groups of polyesterases, thereby expanding the biochemical diversity of biocatalysts for enzymatic polyester depolymerization.

Environmental implication

Synthetic polyesters including PET are widely used polymers, which quickly accumulate in the environment resulting in pollution and causing harm to natural ecosystems. The most sustainable way for preventing plastic pollution and material loss is a closed-loop recycling process including physical, chemical, and enzymatic plastic depolymerization and material recovery. In this study, we have identified 25 bacterial polyesterases with hydrolytic activity against different polyesters and also demonstrated that six known PETases show high activity toward other polyesters. The discovery of novel natural polyester-degrading enzymes and engineering more active and thermostable variants contribute to the development of a closed-loop polyester recycling industry.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2024.136540](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2024.136540).

Data Availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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